

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Project title: Nanocluster formation in oxide particle reinforced steels by internal oxidation after ultrasonic atomization

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2 Summary

The aim of this project was to investigate a novel approach for producing oxide dispersion strengthened (ODS) steels through ultrasonic atomization (UA) capable of addressing critical disadvantages of mechanical alloying (MA) namely higher O and N uptake and inhomogeneous oxide distribution [1–5]. The advantages of UA, such as high sphericity of the powder, narrow particle size distribution, and reduced O and N uptake [6], make it a promising alternative for the MA route. Therefore, a ferritic Fe-14Cr-0.4Ti-0.5Y (in wt.%) ODS alloy was produced by UA under continuous Ar flow. Instead of using Y_2O_3 powder, Y was introduced to the alloy in elemental form or as a Fe_2Y master alloy. Ti was alloyed to investigate the potential formation of Y-Ti-O type nanoclusters as previously reported in MA ODS alloys [7]. The formation of Y-rich oxides through internal oxidation along with their formation mechanism, chemical and thermal stability, and spatial distribution was investigated.

UA successfully produces $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$ oxides in the atomized powder, however not as nanoclusters but in the form of about 100 nm sized precipitates. The oxide dispersoids primarily solidify from the liquid with the residual O from the Ar flow during UA. The dispersoids remain chemically and thermally stable (up to 1130 °C) during heat treatment and sintering. Additionally, complex oxynitrides of much lower volume fraction and intermetallic dispersoids ($Fe_{10}Cr_2Y$) were also formed during atomization. The homogenous nucleation and growth of the oxide dispersoids from the liquid successfully results in a uniform distribution in individual powder particles. However, number density and size of the oxides vary significantly due to non-uniform Y concentration among individual powder particles. These observations were consistent in powder produced via both processing routes (route 1: elemental Y, route 2: Fe_2Y).

Das Ziel dieses Projekts war es, einen neuen Ansatz zur Herstellung von oxid-dispersionsgehärteten (ODS) Stählen durch Ultraschallverdüsung (UA) zu untersuchen. Damit sollen Nachteile des etablierten, mechanischen Legierens (MA) adressiert werden, nämlich höhere Sauerstoff- und Stickstoffaufnahme und erhebliche Gewichtsverluste während des Entgasungsprozesses sowie inhomogene Oxidverteilung [1–5]. Die Vorteile von UA, wie hohe Sphärizität der Pulver, enge Partikelgrößenverteilung und reduzierte Sauerstoff- und Stickstoffaufnahme [6], machen diese Verdüsungsart zu einer vielversprechenden Alternative zur Herstellung von ODS-Stählen gegenüber MA. Hierzu wurde ein ferritischer Fe-14Cr-0.4Ti-0.5Y (in Gew.-%) ODS-Stahl durch UA unter einem kontinuierlichen Ar-Strom verdüst. Anstatt Y_2O_3 -Pulver zu verwenden, wurde Y in elementarer Form und als Fe_2Y -Vorlegierung in die Legierung eingebracht. Ti wurde in die Legierungszusammensetzung aufgenommen, um die mögliche Bildung von Y-Ti-O-Nanoclustern zu untersuchen [7].

Die Bildung Y-reicher Oxide durch interne Oxidation unter Verwendung von gelöstem Sauerstoff wurde erfolgreich nachgewiesen sowie deren Bildungsmechanismus, chemische und thermische Stabilität und räumliche Verteilung untersucht. Der Sauerstoff im Gasstrom während der Zerstäubung ist ausreichend, um die Bildung von Oxiden direkt aus der Schmelze heraus zu ermöglichen. Diese Oxid-Dispersoide sind chemisch und thermisch bis zu 1130 °C während der Wärmebehandlung und des Sinterns stabil. Zusätzlich wurden komplexe Oxy-nitride von geringem Volumengehalt und intermetallische Dispersoide ($Fe_{10}Cr_2Y$) nachgewiesen.

Die Oxide bilden sich durch homogene Keimbildung und Wachstum aus der Schmelze, was zu einer gleichmäßigen Verteilung der Oxide in den einzelnen Pulverpartikeln führt. Allerdings variieren Anzahldichte und Größe der Oxide erheblich aufgrund der ungleichmäßigen Y-Verteilung zwischen den Pulverpartikel. Abschließend konnte gezeigt werden, dass unterschiedliche Wege zur Y-Zugabe (elementares Y sowie über eine Fe_2Y Vorlegierung) ähnliche Ergebnisse in Bezug auf die gebildeten Oxide, ihre chemische und thermische Stabilität und ihre räumliche Verteilung bewirken.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Objective of the project

The project's objective was to explore a new pathway to manufacture the oxide dispersion strengthened (ODS) Fe-Cr alloy using ultrasonic atomization (UA) technique. With the approach outlined in the proposal, the following questions were to be addressed and answered:

Q1: In what form are Y and Ti present in the atomized powder? Have these elements already formed oxides, or are they present in the form of solid solution?

Q2: What O content can be achieved in the UA process, and is the O content achieved during UA enough to form oxides?

Q3: At which stage of the processing route do oxides form? Does the controlled internal oxidation lead to a homogeneous distribution of oxides?

Q4: How does the microstructure evolve through the process, especially in terms of grain size and dislocation density and how they differ from the mechanically alloyed variants?

Q5: How does the novel processing route affect the room temperature mechanical properties of the alloy?

3.2 Materials synthesis and microstructure of drop cast rods

The powder production via UA was first attempted by atomizing multiple batches of Fe-14Cr-0.4Ti-0.25Y (wt.%). However, neither Y nor Y_2O_3 were detected in global chemical (by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy, ICP-OES) and atom probe tomography (APT) analyses in the resulting powder. To address this issue, a higher content of Y was used in the starting composition not only in the elemental form but also in the form of a Fe_2Y master alloy. The selected alloy composition is shown in Table 1. Hereafter, the respective alloy synthesized with the different approaches will be referred to as ODS-Y (utilizing elemental Y) and ODS- Fe_2Y (utilizing Fe_2Y master alloy).

Table 1: Desired composition of the ferritic ODS- and ODS- Fe_2Y alloys.

Type	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y
wt. %	85.1	14.0	0.40	0.50
at. %	84.3	14.9	0.46	0.31

The impurity (O and N) content in the raw materials was measured using carrier gas hot extraction (CGHE), shown in Table 2. The O content in Fe, Cr and Ti used is low (<0.1 wt.%), while the elemental Y used in the study has a significantly higher concentration of O.

The alloys were synthesized through repetitive arc melting on a water-cooled copper mold in an Ar atmosphere of purity 99.998 vol. % (Ar4.8) using an AM/0.5 furnace (Edmund Bühler GmbH, Germany). The purities of the constituents (Fe, Cr, Ti and Y) were 99.95 %. The Fe_2Y master alloy was synthesized in the same way as the target alloys. The arc-melted buttons were then drop-cast into cylindrical rods of 10 mm diameter and 120 mm height in a water-

cooled suction mold. To obtain an adequate amount of powder, four identical rods were drop-cast. The composition of the top and bottom ends of the rods were carefully investigated via ICP-OES and CGHE prior to UA. This is done to monitor the compositional homogeneity of the rods before UA. The compositions of the rods' ends and the average compositions (Table 3) are homogeneous irrespective of the processing route.

Table 2: O and N content in the raw materials obtained by CGHE.

Raw materials	O / wt. %	N / wt. %
Fe	0.0136 ± 0.0011	0.0003 ± 0.0010
Cr	0.0118 ± 0.0020	0.0003 ± 0.0001
Ti	0.0181 ± 0.0016	0.0022 ± 0.0002
Y	0.8230 ± 0.0420	0.0070 ± 0.0010
Fe ₂ Y	0.0620 ± 0.0103	0.0023 ± 0.0003

The microstructure of the rods was analyzed via backscattered electron contrast imaging (SEM-BSE) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS). The cross sections of rods show dendritic solidification microstructures (Figure 1), characterized by large regions that exhibit a darker contrast (dendrite core, confirmed ferritic by X-ray diffraction) and bright interdendritic regions appearing both along the grain boundaries and in the grain interiors. SEM-EDS verify substantial Y enrichment in the interdendritic regions and an according depletion in the dendrites (Figure 1e and Table 4). Furthermore, crystallographic analysis of the Y-rich phase (in Figure 1f) confirms the formation of intermetallic Fe₁₀Cr₂Y (ThMn₁₂ prototype, space group 139).

With respect to respect to Q1 and Q3, it is concluded that Y is mostly present in the form of Y-containing intermetallic phases. No substantial amounts of Y-containing oxides were found in the cast condition. Since no oxide particles were observed, the detected O is likely dissolved in the ferritic matrix.

Table 3: Chemical composition top and bottom end of rods for the ODS-Y alloy obtained by ICP-OES and CGHE. ODS-Fe₂Y yields similar results (no shown here).

Condition	Average composition / wt. %						
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N	
Rod 1	Top	84.1 ± 1.0	13.6 ± 0.2	0.40 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.01	0.004 ± 0.002	<0.001
	Bottom	84.3 ± 0.8	13.8 ± 0.3	0.40 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.01	0.005 ± 0.001	<0.001
Rod 2	Top	83.0 ± 0.1	13.9 ± 0.1	0.41 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.02	0.022 ± 0.002	0.002 ± 0.001
	Bottom	82.7 ± 0.1	13.8 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.02	0.007 ± 0.001	<0.001
Rod 3	Top	82.8 ± 0.2	13.9 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.02	0.015 ± 0.001	0.002 ± 0.001
	Bottom	82.7 ± 0.4	13.8 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.01	0.51 ± 0.09	0.005 ± 0.003	<0.001
Rod 4	Top	82.4 ± 0.1	13.8 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.01	0.013 ± 0.001	<0.001
	Bottom	82.6 ± 0.3	13.9 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.01	0.005 ± 0.001	<0.001

Table 4: Average composition of matrix and interdendritic regions obtained by SEM-EDS.

Position	Average Composition / wt. %			
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y
Dendrites	85.2 ± 0.5	14.2 ± 0.1	0.36 ± 0.03	0
Inter-dendritic regions	80.8 ± 0.5	12.1 ± 0.1	0.42 ± 0.04	6.56 ± 0.09

Figure 1: SEM-BSE micrographs of the (a,c) top and (b,d) bottom section of the drop-cast rod of ODS-Y and ODS-Fe₂Y alloy showing dendritic solidification, (e) SEM-EDS highlighting Y enrichment in interdendritic regions, and (f) crystallographic analysis of the intermetallic phase formed in the interdendritic regions with bright contrast.

3.3 Atomized and processed powder

The UA process was carried out using an ATOLab+ (3DLab Ltd.) system. The chamber was evacuated to an O content of about 10 ppm, then filled with Ar4.8. The O content was measured by trace oxygen analyzers attached to the chamber of the ATO machine. A platform with steel insert was used. The machine was operated at a vibration frequency of 35 kHz and an amplitude of 60 % and an arc current of 100 A (at arc light up) up to 165 A. The entire atomization process was carried out under continuously flowing Ar4.8 atmosphere with a flow rate of 25 l/min. The rods were systematically fed into the atomization chamber; a small part of the rod was then melted by an electric arc and deposited on the steel insert. The deposited material is maintained in the molten state using the movable arc. The ultrasonic vibration is transferred from the cold end of the sonotrode towards the hot end, which forms capillary waves on the surface of the molten pool. Once the critical vibration amplitude is reached, the droplets were ejected into the flowing Ar stream, which cools them instantly and carries them to the cyclone chamber. Further details of the ATO machine can be found in Ref. [6]. The powder was collected in the sealed chamber and transferred to a glove box all under Ar4.8 atmosphere.

To heat treat the as-atomized powder (AA), a Mo foil envelope was created, the powder was then placed inside this Mo envelope. The powder-containing envelope was then heat treated

at 1100 °C for 1 h in a resistance tube furnace, employing three evacuation–backfilling cycles followed by continuous Ar4.8 flow to minimize further oxidation. The heat treatment (HT) was performed to investigate one of two possible scenarios. (i) The heat treatment may facilitate nucleation and growth if the oxide dispersoids are not formed during atomization. (ii) The heat treatment enables examination of possible changes in composition and size if such dispersoids are already present after atomization.

Figures 2a-b show the top view of AA. The average diameter of powders is (59 ± 10) and (68 ± 14) μm for ODS-Y and ODS-Fe₂Y, respectively. AA of both alloys maintain a high sphericity of 0.90 ± 0.07 . The cross-sectional SEM-BSE images reveal three notable observations: (i) The powder particles appear dense and nearly pore-free. (ii) The powder particles contain uniformly distributed dispersoids, however, (iii) their number density varies among different powder particles. The dark phase suggests enrichment in lighter elements while the bright phase is inferred to have a higher concentration of Y compared to the surrounding matrix. As ODS-Y and ODS-Fe₂Y alloys showed identical results with respect to powder synthesis, the further report is restricted to the ODS-Y material. The dispersoids are stable and similarly obtained in HT, see Figure 3.

The chemical composition of AA and HT powders are given in Table 5. Notably, a loss of 0.2 wt.% Y in atomized powder compared to the drop cast rods is observed (see Tables 3 and 5). This is consistent with observations made in the initial trials at 0.25 wt.% Y, where no Y was found in powders after atomization. Furthermore, the O content increased to (0.079 ± 0.001) wt.%. This O content from the small uptake during casting rods and additional uptake during atomization despite the < 10 ppm level O maintained during UA. The total O content is still lower obtained after typical MA processes, e.g. 0.297 wt.% excess O and 0.220 wt.% N [8].

Figure 2: SEM-BSE micrographs of top view of atomized powders of (a) ODS-Y and (b) ODS-Fe₂Y alloy (insets shows SEM-SE images) showing spherical powder particles, (c and d) cross-section view of powders and (e and f) magnified images showing uniformly distributed dispersoids in both alloys.

Figure 3: SEM-BSE micrographs of (a) top-view of HT ODS-Y powder showing partially agglomerated spherical powders, (b) cross-sectional view and (c) magnified image showing uniformly distributed dispersoids.

Table 5: Chemical composition of AA and HT powder conditions obtained by ICP-OES and CGHE

Specimen Condition	Average composition / wt. %					
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N
AA	83.4 ± 0.2	13.2 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.01	0.079 ± 0.001	0.0030 ± 0.0001
HT	84.7 ± 0.5	13.0 ± 0.1	0.41 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.01	0.102 ± 0.012	0.006 ± 0.001

APT samples were prepared from both AA and HT powder with medium particle number density. The isosurfaces, shown in Figures 4a-b, reveal three distinct dispersoid types (i) a complex oxynitride (Dispersoid 1), (ii) a Y-Ti-O type oxide (Disp. 2), and (iii) a Fe-Cr-Y intermetallic (Disp. 3). The composition of these dispersoids is given Table 6. The number of nitrides is expected to be at least one order of magnitude lower than that of the oxides due to the O:N ratio. The oxide phase has a composition of $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$. Figure 4c shows the APT measurements for HT powders. The composition of Disp. 4 closely resembles that of the oxide in AA, which indicates good thermal stability of $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$ oxide.

Figure 4: Reconstructed map of APT dataset containing elemental distribution maps, isosurface constructions and one-dimensional concentration profiles for dispersoids in (a,b) AA and (c) HT powder.

Table 6: Chemical composition (in at.%) of Disp. 1-4 in Figure 4 and their surrounding matrix.

Position	Average composition / at. %					
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N
Disp. 1	11.6 ± 1.1	0.9 ± 0.1	0.05 ± 0.02	62.7 ± 3.4	3.3 ± 0.9	20.4 ± 2.1
Disp. 2	1.5 ± 0.9	0.02 ± 0.00	9.67 ± 1.20	41.9 ± 2.3	45.2 ± 1.9	0.04 ± 0.02
Matrix	83.5 ± 3.2	14.9 ± 2.1	1.30 ± 0.50	0.09 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.06	0
Disp. 3	80.2 ± 3.3	6.34 ± 1.20	1.40 ± 0.50	11.6 ± 2.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0
Matrix	84.1 ± 2.8	13.3 ± 1.9	1.30 ± 0.42	0.010 ± 0.001	0.20 ± 0.05	0
Disp. 4	3.8 ± 0.8	0.8 ± 0.1	9.2 ± 1.3	41.5 ± 2.5	44.3 ± 4.1	0.01 ± 0.01
Matrix	84.8 ± 2.4	14.7 ± 1.6	0.40 ± 0.19	0.050 ± 0.002	0.20 ± 0.02	0

The crystal structure of the intermetallic phase was determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) conducted using a Tecnai F20 G2 SuperTwin microscope (ThermoFisher, USA) operated at 200 kV. The dispersoid captured in TEM shares the same crystal structure (ThMn_{12} prototype) as the intermetallic phase identified in the as-cast condition (Figure 1).

The research questions Q1 to Q2 were successfully answered. Y is almost completely consumed in oxide formation, resulting in a matrix that is depleted of Y. In contrast, a portion of Ti is consumed in oxide (and to lesser extent oxynitride) formation, while the remainder stays in solid solution. While the O uptake during atomization can be kept at much lower level as compared to other established powder metallurgical routes, the O content is still sufficient to partially oxidize Y. Although thermally stable oxide dispersoids were formed during the UA process, they do not occur in the form of nanoclusters. Furthermore, a Y-rich intermetallic phase was successfully identified in the powder.

Figure 5: (a) TEM bright field micrograph showing Fe-Cr-Ti intermetallic and (b) the corresponding SAD pattern.

3.4 Consolidated specimen and inhomogeneity in dispersoid distribution

To produce solid bulk samples, the powder from the AA condition was consolidated using field assisted sintering (FAST, 1130 °C/50 MPa/5 min) to obtain a bulk pellet with a diameter of 20 mm and a height of 10 mm. Initial consolidation at 1100 °C (consistent with HT conditions) resulted in incompletely sintered pellets with significant porosity (3.2 ± 0.9 vol.%), so the temperature was increased to 1130 °C, lowering the porosity to (0.7 ± 0.2) vol.%. SEM-BSE micrographs of FAST sample show former powder particles with varying dispersoid number density, classified as low, medium, and high. From the compositional analysis using SEM-EDS, see Table 7, a clear relationship emerges: particles with high dispersoid density possess an elevated Y content (2.5 wt.%). In contrast, Y was not detected in particles with very low dispersoid density. Detailed statistics on the particle distributions are incorporated in a publicly available preprint, see Section 4.2. The low dispersoid density powder particles also have the lowest grain size and vice versa, see Table 7.

Figure 6: SEM-BSE images of FAST sample showing former powder particles with varying spatial distribution of oxides. (a) and (b) are different locations.

Table 7: Composition analysis and average grain size of marked powders in Figure 6 by SEM-EDS.

Dispersoid density	Average Composition / wt. %				Avg. grain size / μm
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	
Low (P1 and P4)	85.4 ± 0.3	14.3 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0	17.4 ± 4.1
Medium (P3 and P6)	85.2 ± 0.3	13.9 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	8.0 ± 2.3
High (P2 and P5)	83.8 ± 0.3	13.0 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 1.5

3.5 Formation mechanism of oxides

The observed 0.2 wt. % loss of Y from drop casting to the AA powder (Tables 3 and 5) can be explained by an inhomogeneous distribution of Y in the powder particles (Figure 6). Given the similar melting points of Fe, Cr, Ti and Y [9], selective evaporation of Y is unlikely. The primary reason for Y inhomogeneity is attributed to convection and diffusion in the liquid during UA (the Y content in all other processing steps is stable). During the ultrasonic atomization process, the alloy on top of the sonotrode is maintained in a molten state for approximately 3-5 min. An inhomogeneous temperature distribution by the heating through the arc can lead to convection and variation in Y concentration between powder particles atomized from the top and bottom regions of a single melt pool. This was verified by the compositional analysis of the left-over material in the ATO with much higher Y concentration (in the form of the Y-containing intermetallic phase) than in the initial alloys, see Table 8.

Table 8: Left-over material in ATO investigated by SEM-BSE and SEM-EDS.

Elements	Overall Composition / wt. %
Fe	82.9 ± 0.2
Cr	14.4 ± 0.1
Ti	0.4 ± 0.1
Y	2.3 ± 1.7

The formation of $\text{Y}_{42}\text{Ti}_{10}\text{O}_{45}$ oxide is expected to happen mostly during atomization. No significant further internal oxidation occurred during subsequent thermal exposures. There are only two possible routes for the dispersoids to form via nucleation and growth during the atomization process: (i) primary solidification of the dispersoids in the liquid phase prior to matrix solidification and (ii) precipitation of the dispersoids from the solid phase after the matrix solidifies first. In case of solid-state nucleation, the incoherent oxides would have preferentially formed at the grain boundaries. However, the uniform distribution of oxides with no preference to grain boundaries hints at their formation in liquid state. The cooling rate during UA is very fast and

is expected to be comparable to gas atomization (10^6 K/s [10,11]). Assuming a temperature drop of 500 K for the oxide formation, the calculated growth time is approximately $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s. Given the small diffusion distance of 1.4 nm in the solid state, the nucleation and growth of oxides of roughly 100 nm are practically not feasible. In contrast, the diffusion distance in the liquid state is approximately 13 μm , as a result of significantly enhanced atomic mobility in the liquid state. Nucleation and growth of oxides in the liquid state is the likely formation mechanism of the Y-Ti oxide. As the melting point of $\text{Y}_{42}\text{Ti}_{10}\text{O}_{45}$ oxide is expected to be comparable to that of Y_2O_3 , approximately 2400 °C [12], it is very likely that the oxide dispersoids will solidify prior to the solidification of the surrounding matrix.

With respect to research questions Q3 and Q4, the following conclusion can be drawn: The process successfully produces homogeneously distributed oxides in individual powder particles, already during the atomization process. In comparison to MA, no nanocluster formation occurs as the oxides most likely form from the liquid. The grain size of the powders widely varies among individual powder particles as the number density of oxide particles varies due to Y inhomogeneity in the melt pool. The inhomogeneous distribution of Y within AA is caused by the dynamics of handling the liquid during the atomization process.

3.6 References

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

[a] S. Seils, A. Kauffmann, W. Delis, T. Boll, M. Heilmaier, Microstructure and mechanical properties of high-Mn-ODS steels, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 825 (2021) 141859.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2021.141859>

[b] S. Sen, S. Dixit, M. Muench, L. Yang, C. Somsen, S. Seils, D. Schliephake, A. Kauffmann, M. Heilmaier, A novel synthesis pathway for oxide dispersion strengthened Fe–Cr alloys enabled by ultrasonic atomization, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* (2026) 188928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2026.188928>.

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

[c] S. Sen, S. Dixit, M. Muench, L. Yang, C. Somsen, S. Seils, D. Schliephake, A. Kauffmann, M. Heilmaier, Public dataset on “A novel synthesis pathway for oxide dispersion strengthened Fe–Cr alloys enabled by ultrasonic atomization” (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19217212>.

[d] S. Sen, S. Dixit, M. Muench, L. Yang, C. Somsen, S. Seils, D. Schliephake, A. Kauffmann, M. Heilmaier, Public dataset on this report “Nanocluster formation in oxide particle reinforced steels by internal oxidation after ultrasonic atomization” (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20157576>.

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

None.